

E.W.E.N.T. – Event Waste Elimination in No Time

Jakob Wulff, Carina Lindahl & Otto Exner

¹DTU Design Engineering, Technical University of Denmark

INTRODUCTION

The idea of the garbage bag E.W.E.N.T. was developed in the course "Brugerorienteret design" in our first semester at Technical University of Denmark.

E.W.E.N.T. is a waste solution, focusing on special occasions and happenings, where the amount of waste is especially heavy. The bin is easily installed or dismantled in less than a minute. Having a light construction, it is consisting of a minimum of material, and the disposable bin is thrown out with the garbage when it has served its time, which is from one to three days.

THEORY, METHODS AND RESULT

Using the SCOT theory we analyzed interviews and observations and discovered some problems in Copenhagen. From this analysis of our collected material we saw clearly that the capacities of the existing bins were not sufficient enough in specific situations, such as events. The present concept of E.W.E.N.T. was developed through idea generation and concept validations.

The great thing about E.W.E.N.T. is that it can be installed all over the city. With its elastic/strip it can be tied to lamp posts, trees or fences for example - wherever there is a need.

E.W.E.N.T. has a short, but an environmentally conscious LCC. The product is made of polyethylene, often used for disposable material, like disposable cutlery, as the complete combustion results in only CO₂ and H₂O and is easy to mass-produce in an environmentally correct way. The concept can be implemented in the current waste handling system in Copenhagen. Furthermore the advantages of the disposable aspect of E.W.E.N.T. is that it takes up less room and weighs less compared to other bins suitable for events, and it does not have to be transported to stocks, all which minimizes the cost and pollution of transport considerably.

CONCLUSION

E.W.E.N.T. is a garbage solution for special occasions, and is designed to be disposable, without any major environmental effect. It is a solution that will keep the area around the event much more clean, because of its mounting aspect and light weight. Compared to other existing solutions E.W.E.N.T. redefine the way we think about bins, and solves the problems in a new and better way.